

BCNP: Rethinking Network Communication—A Bitcoin-Based Protocol for the Post-IP Era

Abstract

The rapid growth of connected devices, IoT ecosystems, and decentralized applications has revealed critical limitations in today's IP-based networking architecture. Issues such as IPv4 address exhaustion, reliance on complex NAT mechanisms, and the stagnation of IPv6 adoption have hindered scalability and security. These challenges highlight the need for a future-proof alternative that offers security, scalability, and decentralization while bypassing traditional IP-based vulnerabilities.

This paper introduces the Bitcoin Communication Network Protocol (BCNP)—a decentralized addressing and transport stack designed to replace TCP/IP and address the needs of next-generation secure networks. BCNP leverages cryptographically verifiable identifiers, dynamic routing, and the Lightning Network (LN) to establish secure, peer-to-peer communication without reliance on IP infrastructure.

BCNP introduces a 20-byte address structure inspired by the NSAP format, dynamically assigning prefixes based on hashed LN public keys and ensuring tamper-proof identities using Bitcoin signatures. Address legitimacy is validated via decentralized records, replacing centralized systems like RPKI. To maintain scalability and minimize blockchain bloat, IPFS (Inter-Planetary File System) is proposed as a distributed storage layer, with pointers anchored in Bitcoin or LN transactions.

By separating the control plane (route discovery via LN channels) from the data plane (payload delivery over Ethernet or Internet tunnels), BCNP ensures dynamic path selection while maintaining efficient data transmission. Future enhancements include multi-hop routing, dynamic tunneling, and channel-based routing for scalable, trustless networks. In the long term, BCNP could also be adopted as the infrastructure backbone for Bitcoin and Lightning Network nodes, eliminating IP dependencies and enabling truly decentralized communication frameworks.

1. Introduction

Today's communication networks rely heavily on the TCP/IP stack, which is becoming increasingly inflexible and centralized. With the depletion of IPv4 addresses, challenges in IPv6 adoption, and reliance on NAT, traditional architectures struggle to meet the needs of modern, decentralized systems.

This paper introduces BCNP as an alternative communication model based on Bitcoin and the Lightning Network (LN). It eliminates the dependency on IP routing and provides decentralized, cryptographically secure addressing for scalable communication.

2. BCNP Address

The BCNP address follows a hierarchical 20-byte structure derived from the ISO CLNP/NSAP model:

Field	Size	Source	Example
AFI/IDI	13 bytes	Hashed LN Public Key (SHA-256)	BA.18.BA.87.3B.EB.39.C7.3A.CA.F2.CB.24
System ID	6 bytes	MAC Address of Device	52.54.00.65.43.21
Selector	1 byte	Static Zero (00)	00

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NSAP Address Structure:
<----IDP----> <-----DSP----->
                <-----HO-DSP----->
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| AFI | IDI | Contents assigned by authority identified in IDI field |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
<-----Area Address-----> <----ID----> <-SEL->

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BCNP Address Structure:
<-----Prefix-----> <-----System ID-----> <Selector>
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| LN-HASH (13 bytes, SHA-256) | MAC Address (6 bytes) | 00 |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+

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3. Address Registration and Legitimacy

BCNP introduces Bitcoin-based verification for address legitimacy, replacing centralized RPKI systems.

1. Decentralized Registration:
 - o BCNP addresses are hashed and stored using IPFS for scalability.
 - o Pointers to these addresses are anchored in Bitcoin transactions or LN invoices.
2. Cryptographic Security:
 - o Public keys associated with BCNP addresses ensure tamper-proof authentication using digital signatures.
3. Routing Trust Model:
 - o Future routing algorithms can use signature validation to ensure packets are not spoofed and destinations are legitimate.

4. Implementation and Results

The BCNP protocol uses dynamic prefix generation from LN public keys combined with MAC addresses for local identification. It operates over Ethernet frames without relying on TCP/IP.

Key Features:

- Dynamic Address Assignment: Derived from LN keys and device MAC addresses.
- Raw Ethernet Transmission: Direct communication using custom Ethertype (0xFEFE).

- Tamper-Proof Security: Enforced via Bitcoin signatures.

Results:

- Successfully demonstrated packet transmission between hosts using dynamic BCNP addresses.
- Verified prefix consistency and data integrity without IP-based routing.

5. Control and Data Plane Separation

BCNP separates routing decisions (control plane) from data delivery (data plane):

- Control Plane:
 - Uses LN payment channels for route discovery and verification.
 - Ensures that only legitimate addresses are accepted via Bitcoin-based validation.
- Data Plane:
 - Transmits payloads directly over Ethernet or via Internet tunnels for scalability.
 - Keeps data independent of control paths for efficiency and flexibility.

6. Use Cases

1. Aviation Networks:
 - Secure, delay-tolerant air traffic communications.
2. Financial Systems:
 - Blockchain-native financial systems requiring secure identities.
3. Military and Defense:
 - Fault-tolerant and encrypted data exchanges.
4. IoT and Smart Cities:
 - Scalable infrastructure for autonomous systems.

7. Future Work

- Tunneling Over Public Internet:
 - Encapsulation techniques for incremental deployment.
- Multi-Hop Routing:
 - Dynamic path forwarding using signature verification.
- Address Renewal:
 - Mechanisms for re-registration and revocation.
- BCNP as a Foundation for Future Bitcoin and Lightning Infrastructure
 - As BCNP gains adoption, it has the potential to serve as the underlying infrastructure not just for standalone networks, but also for Bitcoin and Lightning Network (LN) nodes themselves. This would eliminate dependencies on IP-based systems, enabling end-to-end decentralized addressing and communication.
 - In such a scenario, Bitcoin miners and LN routing nodes could transition from IP addressing to BCNP addressing, leveraging its built-in cryptographic authentication and tamper-proof identity verification.

- This transition could simplify network management, reduce reliance on centralized ISPs, and enhance resilience against attacks like DDoS—paving the way for a truly decentralized Internet infrastructure built on Bitcoin principles.
- Further research will be required to evaluate the feasibility of integrating BCNP addressing into Bitcoin Core and Lightning Network implementations.

8. Conclusion

BCNP offers a scalable, decentralized, and tamper-proof alternative to TCP/IP. Leveraging Bitcoin's ledger and Lightning Network, it provides dynamic addressing, cryptographic authentication, and flexible routing models. Future extensions include tunneling, multi-hop routing, and channel-based paths, paving the way for its adoption as a next-generation communication protocol.